

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Need analysis: A case study of students' formative assessment at SMP Negeri 1 Mananggu, Indonesia

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Abstract

Formative Assessment are very important in the learning process. Through this formative assessment, students can measure their learning and the teacher can make improvements toward their quality of learning. The student's ability to complete a test is a very important role, therefore students' English skill is the language skills that are needed in evaluation.

Thus, this study is aimed to show what are the students' goal, what are the target and the learning needs in measuring their English skill. The result were, the students want to have more pictures in their formative assesment and the students want to do the formative test through offline class.

Keywords: Formative Assessment; Target needs; Learning needs

1. Introduction

An assessment or so-called assessment is a way or a tool to get information about the attainment and the competence of learners. The purpose of assessment is to see the accomplishment of learners to compile an appropriate learning program. One way and another tool that can be used in this regard by using a test. Everything to do with the evaluation is identified with the formative. A test is a tool or procedure used to know or measure things in the world of education of learners. The learned quality of students is determined by the attainment of students' learning.

The formative in evaluating student learning outcomes is not just a description of students' achievement but is a measure of the quality of the learning carried out. So, that can be an improvement in the quality of further learning. The evaluation that is used as the basis for making improvements to the teaching and learning process is known as an assessment for learning. The teachers can use formative assessment as an instrument for evaluating learning.

Formative assessment is very important in the learning process. Through this formative, students can measure their learning and the teacher can make improvements toward their quality of learning. On the other, Formative assessment becomes feedback on the learning process.

The student's ability to complete a formative is a very important role, therefore students' English skill is the language skills that are needed in evaluation. Whether or not students complete a formative depends on their ability. The process of processing information is obtained from their ability. The language learners know their values and needs are described in the result of their evaluation. To solve the problems above, students' formative assessment will be the one that determines the success of students in encountering the learning process. Therefore, the teacher has to conduct a need analysis in order to solve the problems.

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In relation to the need analysis, the study by Rasuna, et al (2018) stated that if the lecture could not scrutinize students' problem, it will give bad impact towards students' quality in faculty, mainly students are incompetent in understanding the materials and hardly to explore their skill in English. Therefore, the lecturer's way to help students in learning English optimally is started from students' need analysis in learning English in the class.

Additionally, as cited in Nunan in 1988, needs analysis is procedure or process in collecting the information about students' need that will be used as the basis for curriculum development to answer the learning needs of a certain group of students.

Moreover, according to Basturkmen (2010) as cited in Rasuna, et al (2018) explain that the need analysis process involves asking questions about the target situations, discourse analysis, learners factors and information about the students' motivation, how they learn and their perception of theory needs and it includes context analysis.

In addition, Nation and Macalister (2010, p.25) cited in Rasuna, et al (2018) agree that need analysis is directed mainly at the goals and content of a course. It examines what the learners know already and what they need to know. Need analysis make sure that the course will contain relevant and useful things to learn. This analysis could be the data bank in designing instructional sets, such as syllabus, Semester Learning Plan, students' worksheet, media, assesment, and learning materials.

2. Literature review

2.1. Assessment

Assessment is the process of gathering information for improvement. Moreover, according to Arends (2012: 217) Assessment is the process of gathering information about students and classes for educational decisions and as fair judgments about students learning. It means, assessment as a tool for improving the quality of education. Another, Boud 1990; Brown 1997, Gibs and Simpson 1994 in Anne Campbel and Lin Norton, 2007 said that assessment is the heart of the learning process. So, assessment is an important part of learning.

According to Brown (2001:4) assessment is a student's response to a question and performance of students ability. Besides that, He divided the assessment into two parts; formal and informal assessment. Formal assessment is a systematically planned technique constructed to give teachers and students an appraisal of student achievement. Whereas, informal assessment is unplanned comments or responses without recording results and making a judgment about students' competence.

2.2. Kinds of assessment

Types of tests based on functions in the implementation of learning are also divided into two parts; there is summative and formative assessment.

2.3. Summative assessment

Summative assessment is measuring the student's competence at the end of a course. Summative tests are carried out with the aim of thoroughly evaluating the success of the implementation of learning. The purpose of the summative assessment is also to measure and summarize what students have learned (Brown:2003). An example of a summative is a final semester assessment and a final test for the final level.

2.4. Formative assessment

formative assessment is measuring the student's competence and skill in the learning process to help them to improve the quality of learning. The effective formative assessment involves 1). teachers making adjustments to teaching and learning in response to assessment evidence. 2) students receiving feedback about their learning with advice on what they can do to improve, and 3) students' participation in the process through self-assessment.

Brown (2001) states that the test is the way or method to measure someone's skill, knowledge, and performance. The formative test is the test which use to measure the student's achievement in one competence and it is as the teachers' feedback. According to Brown (2001), the purpose of a criterion-referenced test is to measure the amount of learning that a student has accomplished on each objective.

2.5. Need Analysis

According to Richard (2001), "procedures used to collect information about learners' needs are known as needs analysis". There are several purposes that Richard (2001) explains in purposes of need analysis:

- To find out what language skills a learner needs in order to perform a particular role, such as a sales manager, tour guide, or university student.
- To collect information about a particular problem learners are experiencing.
- To identify a gap between what students are able to do and what they need to be able to do.
- To determine if an existing course adequately addresses the needs of potential students.
- To determine which students from a group really need of training in particular language skills.
- To identify a change of director that people in a reference group feel are important.

In addition, nowadays, the tasks of needs analysis are much more complex, the aim is to gather the learners' information and explain the target situation and the area of ESP. Duddley-Evans and St. John (2009) divide the concept of needs analysis into eight components which are later, categorized into five parts, those are:

- Target situation analysis and objective needs analysis (e.g. tasks and activities learners will use English for);
- Target situation analysis about the learner knowledge in language and skills include linguistic analysis, discourse analysis, and genre analysis;
- Subjective needs analysis, about the learners experience in learning before, the learners want in learning, the learners reasons and expectation in take the subject;
- Present situation analysis to identify learners' current skills and language use;
- Means analysis, i.e. information about the environment where the course will run.

Furthermore, according to Hutchinson and Water (2004, p 55-58), "target needs' is something of an umbrella term, which in practice hides a number of important distinctions". It is very beneficial to look at the target situation in terms of necessities, lacks, and wants.

- Necessities are the type of need determined by the demands of the target situation. Moreover, necessities aim to find out what the learners need to know in the target situation. It is a matter of observing what situations the learner will need and then analyzing the constituent parts of them.
- Lacks to identify difficulties itself, with the needs of particular learners. Also need to know what the learner knows already, and then decide which of the necessities the learner lacks.
- Wants considered target need only in an objective sense, with the actual learners playing no active role. It means that what the learners want or feel they need.

2.6. Target Needs

According to Hutchinson and Water (2004, p 55-58), "target needs' is something of an umbrella term, which in practice hides a number of important distinctions". It is very beneficial to look at the target situation in terms of necessities, lacks, and wants.

2.6.1. Necessities

Necessities are the type of need determined by the demands of the target situation. Moreover, necessities aim to find out what the learners need to know in the target situation. It is a matter of observing what situations the learner will need and then analyzing the constituent parts of them.

2.6.2. Lacks

Lacks is purposed to identify difficulties itself, with the needs of particular learners. Also need to know what the learner knows already, and then decide which of the necessities the learner lacks.

2.6.3. Wants

Wants considered target need only in an objective sense, with the actual learners playing no active role. It means that what the learners want or feel they need.

2.7. Learning Needs

Additionally, learning needs also includes input, procedures, setting, learners' role and teachers' role. Those are known as tasks component in Nunan (2004, p. 40). Nunan (2004, p. 47-70) defines that

- 'Input' refers to the learners work about the subject in completing the task based on spoken, written and visual data. Data can be provided by a teacher, a textbook or some other sources.
- 'Procedures' refers to steps that a learner has to do with the input in the learning task.
- 'Settings' refers to the classroom arrangements specified or implied in the task.
- 'Role' refers to the part that teachers and learners are hoped to play in bringing out the learning tasks in the social and interpersonal relationships between the participants".

Thus, it means that learning need gather what the learners' needs in achieving the effectiveness of teaching and learning process based on the student needs analysis. Based on the the explanation above, need analysis will be beneficial to the researcher to take the student's need analysis which will lead to the target needs and learning needs that the students should achieve at the objective of learning.

3. Material and method

3.1. Research Method

This research is conducted by using qualitative method. In Creswell study in 1994 stated that a qualitative study is defined as an inquiry process of understanding a social or human problem based on building a complex, holistic picture, formed with words, reporting detailed views of informants, and conducted in a natural setting. Additionally, Denzin and Lincoln (1994) stated that qualitative research involves the studies use and collection of a variety of empirical materials case study, personal experience, introspective, life story interview, observational, historical, interactional, and visual texts-that describe routine and problematic moments and meaning in individuals' lives.

Thus, this research is qualitative research because it is a depth research. This research uses qualitative research because qualitative is emphasized the process not the result. The process is important part in every kind of occasions because it takes much time.

3.2. Site and Participant

The site of this study is SMP 1 Mananggu, Boalemo Regency. The participants are 25 students of seventh grade at SMP 1 Mananggu.

3.3. Technique of Data Collection

3.3.1. Interview

In this step, the researcher interviews the English teacher about the use of English formative test in the classroom.

3.3.2. Questionnaire

In this step, the data will be collected through questionnaires. The questionnaire used in this study is the Need analysis questionnaires which is contained the students target needs and learning needs. Moreover, need analysis that the researcher in applied the questionnaire is proposed by Lamb (1996, p 34-8) in Wello and Doliah (2008, p.79), Hutchinson and Waters (1987) and Nunan (2004). Lamb model of questionnaire is explored students' background; include name, age, experience in learning English, duration of use English in everyday, and the students' proficiency level in English. Moreover, Hutchinson Water in explored the target needs include, goals, necessities, lacks and wants. Then, Nunan in explored the learning needs include input, procedures, setting, teachers' role and learners' role. Thus, the form of the questionnaire is adapted from a study by Thalib R (2017). Here are the organization of questionnaire:

Table 1 Questionnaire

NO	Aspect	The Purpose of the Question	References	
1	Responded Background	To find out general learner needs survey	Lamb (1996)	
2	Target Needs	Goal	To find out the reason of learning English	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
		Necessities	To find out the type of the need based on target situation	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
		Lacks	To find out the gap between learners' proficiency and the demand of the target situation	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
		Wants	To find out the learners' want in learning English	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
3	Learning Needs	Input	To find out the input for English speaking worksheet that the students want	Nunan (2004)
		Procedure	To find out the activities that the students like the most	Nunan (2004)
		Setting	To find out the setting of doing the task that the students like the most	Nunan (2004)
		Student's role	To find out the information about the role of the students	Nunan (2004)
		Teacher's role	To find out the information about the role that the teacher should perform	Nunan (2004)

3.4. Technique of Data Analysis

According to Bogdan as cited in Sugiyono (2012) "data analysis is the process of systematically searching and arranging the interview transcript, fieldnotes, and other materials that you accumulate to increase your own understanding of the topic that enable you to present what you have discovered to others" In analyzing the data, the students result of need analysis will help teacher to develop the students curriculum material in helping to achieve the object of learning.

4. Result

This following passages presents the findings and discussions which covers the result of need analysis; target needs and learning needs, as follow:

4.1. Responded Background

The respondent's background is the first thing that the researcher asks before the target needs and learning needs. The responded background involves the students' name, ages, and their experiences in learning English. Their experience in learning English covers their experience in formal school, elementary school, junior high school, and informal school such as an English course.

The result shows that the students most of the students learn English in Junior High School. It means that most of the students are new to English subjects because they did not learn it in Preschool and Elementary School. The seventh grade consists of 25 students. There were 11 male students and 14 female students. They were mostly 13 years old for 11 students and the rest were 15 years old which consisted of two students. The age range from 12 to 15 years old. In addition, only 4 out of 25 students have taken an English course before.

4.2. Target Needs

4.2.1. Goal

Goal refers to the general intentions behind the learning. According to Hutchinson and Waters in 1987, the goal is to find out the reason for learning English. At this point, the goal of learning English skills is presented as follows:

Figure 1 The Goal of Learning English

Chart 1.1 shows the students’ goal or purpose in learning English. This is the question number one of the questionnaire. The data show that students who want to communicate using English is only 38.70%, and students who want to get the best score are 54.83%, while the students who want to get the best score are only 38.70%. students aim to learn English to understand the vocabulary in daily lives with an average of **61.29**. It means that they learn English English skills for their long-term benefits in the future.

4.2.2. Necessity

Necessity is related to what the learners should know or achieve in order to function effectively in the target situation or to find out the type of the need based on the target situation. At this case, there are two questions about necessity. First is the benefits of learning English which will determine their future (Table 1.2). Second is the students’ target situation (Table 1.3). Those are presented as follows:

Figure 2 The Benefits of Learning English

Based on the table above, only 16.12% felt that learning English was to get a good score, and 29.03% felt that learning English helped them to complete the test. While, the students assure that learning English is beneficial for them to understand the learning topic well with an average score of 58.06 out of 100. Rather than finishing the test and reaching the target score, the students think that understanding the learning topic is the most important.

Figure 3 Students' Target Situation

The table above shows about the students' target situation after learning English. As can be seen, only 9.67% felt that learning English helped them to communicate. And about 32.25% felt that they were able to complete the English test. Most of the students believe that they can reach the target score in English as a subject with the average score of 58.06 of 100.

4.2.3. Lack

According to Hutchinson and Water in 1987, lack is aimed to find out the gap between learners' proficiency and the demand of the target situation. At this point, this is about what kind of English ability that the students have. Therefore, the result of the students' lack is presented as follow:

Figure 4 English Ability that the Students Have

Based on the data presented, more than half of the students assumed that they had mastered the vocabulary. It has an average of 54.83 out of 100. Meanwhile, second, most of the students also assumed that they could write the vocabulary well with a 41.93 average.

4.2.4. Want

Want refers to what the learners want to do in learning in the classroom. It supported by Hutchinson and Waters in 1987 which stated that want is aimed to find out the learners’ want in learning english. In this section, the students are asked about what kind of test that the students want the most. It is presented as follow.

Figure 5 Type of Test that the Students Want the Most

According to the data above, there are about 51.61 strongly agree that multiple choice and matching are most favorable in filling out the test but it turns out that most of the students want multiple-choice complex as their kind of test. With 64.51 average in the “agree” section, the students love the multiple choice complex more than any other kinds of test such as multiple choice, matching, short answer, and explanation. Though the short answer and matching also have big averages multiple choice complex is the most favorite.

4.3. Learning Needs

4.3.1. Input

Input is aimed to find out the input for English test that the students want the most. According to Nunan in 2004, input refers to the spoken, written, and visual data that learners work with in the course of completing the task. The question is about type of test that the students love the most. It will become the guide for making the test in order to fulfill the students learning needs. There are two questions of input in this questionnaire. The result is presented at the chart below:

Figure 6 Type of Test that the Students Love the Most

The first input in the questionnaire is about the type of test that the students assumed was easy to finish first. The results showed that 67.74 average students want the multiple choice complex as the type of test. Besides that, they also 64.51 prioritize multiple choice as the students answer first. The second question is the amount of questions in a test that the students can finish in 120 minutes. The result is presented below.

Figure 7 Amount of Question in a Test that The Students Can Finish in 120 minutes

The data presented above shows that the amount of the questions that the students can finish in 120 minutes is 1-5 questions. It has a 74.19 average with o the second most items also has a big average with 5-10 questions and has a 70.96 average.

4.3.2. Procedure

According to Nunan in 2004, procedure specifies what learners will actually do with the input that forms the point of departure for the learning task. The question in the questionnaire is about the way of the students completing the task. In this case the students prefer to do it online or offline. The result is presented below:

Figure 8 Students' Preference to Do the Test By

Based on the data above the students want to do the test in offline test with an average of 77.41. It is known that we face the coronavirus outbreak which has so many fields affected, such as the economy and education. Therefore, school has been canceled and the government has to apply the study from home through online classes. Though the government will resume the classes by doing offline classes, the researcher is interested in asking the students whether they want to do the test online or offline.

4.3.3. Students role

According to Nunan in 2004, role refers to the part that learners are expected to play in carrying out learning tasks as well as the social and interpersonal relationships between the participants. In this questionnaire, the students role is about the way the students do the test. It is presented as follow

Figure 9 The Way Students Do the Test

The data above shows that the students want to answer the easiest question first with a 74.19 average out of 100. The second most votes are from the students who want to answer the questions on time with a 58.06 average score. In addition, 58.06 strongly agreed that during the test the questions were understandable, also it easy to answer.

4.3.4. Teachers role

As well as the students role, according to Nunan in 2004, teachers role are expected to play in carrying out learning tasks as well as the social and interpersonal relationships between the participants. In this questionnaire, the teachers role is about the teachers role in giving the test to the students. The result of the question will be presented in the following chart

Figure 10 The Students Preference of Teacher’s role in Giving the Test

The table above shows that the students want the teacher to put more pictures in the test. As it will attract the students' interest to do the test. The items have a 77.41 average score out of 100. In addition, the test given by the teacher must also have clear instructions, this is shown by 64.51%.

In conclusion, students’ learning needs in English Formative assessment will be presented in the following chart

Figure 11 Conclusion of Students’ Need Analysis in English Formative Assessment

There are ten questions about the student's learning needs. The students mostly want to understand the English vocabulary in daily life (61%), understand the material easily (58%), reach the target score (58%), mastering vocabularies (55%). In doing the test, the students want Multiple Choice Complex (65%) as the type of the text, and the type of the text that they finish first (68%). Furthermore, the amount of questions that the students can finish in 120 minutes is 1-5 questions. Thus, the students prefer the offline class (77%) rather than the online class. Finally, the students want the test should be contained more pictures (77%).

5. Discussion

This part will explain the finding above about the result of the data that the researcher found.

5.1. Responded Background

The responded background is the first thing that the research ask before the target needs and learning needs. The responded background involves the students' name, age, and their experineces in learning English. Their experience in learning English covers their experience in the formal school, elementary school, and the informal school such as an english course. The result shows that only 4 students who had taken an English course before, and most of the students have just learn English in Junior High School. It means that most of the students are new towards English Subject because they did not learn it in Elementary School.

5.2. Target Needs

Target needs covers the students goal, necessities, lack, and want in need analysis questionnaire as what Hutchinson and Waters' (1987) pilar of the target needs. The first is goal. According to the result, the students goal in learning English is to understand the vocabulary in daily lifes with an average of **61.29%**. It means that theses students are interested in learning to know the vocabularies in their daily life. While the second highest is to get a good score and the last is to be able to cummunicate in English.

In the necessities there are two questions. First, the students had asked what benefits that the students can get by learning English. The result shows that the students will understand the material easily (58.6%) rather than doing the test and getting a good score. Second, the students target situation. The students had asked about after learning English the students will have the formative test and what will the students get after that. The result was the students are able to reach the target score. In the next target needs questions are lack and want. The students are asked to measure their own English abilty and what type of test that they want the most. The results are the students are able to master the vocabularies and the the type of the test that the students want the most is multiple choice complex.

In conclusion, the students want to understand the vocabularies well in their daily life, so that they can understand the English very well as well as the material that has been taught by the teacher in the classroom. Thus they want mulitple choice complex the most to be featured in the formative test.

5.3. Learning Needs

There are input, procedure, student's role and teacher's role in the learning needs part. In input part there are two questions. First, the students want to have the muliple choice complex the most as their type of test. Second, the students can finish 1-5 questions in 120 minutes. In the procedure part, the students are asked whether they like to do the test by online or offline. The result is the students want to do the test via offline class.

Moreover, in the students' role part, the students are asked what should they do in doing the test. The result is the students will do the easiest question first. While in teacher's role, the students are asked the preference of the teacher's role in giving the test. The result shows that the teacher should include more pictures in the test.

6. Conclusion

Assesment as one of the tools in measuring students capability in learning has plays an important role in the learning process. The succes of the learning objective can be measured by the assesment whether it is formative or summative test. The problem nowadays is the teacher have not develop the test by their own. It is only taken from the existing book which will make the test old. According to Weir (2005), we need a tool to improve the right test. We should have a minimum requirement for testing practice. So, the variety of forms of the testis a fair solution that can be used to enhance the student's English skills. The student not only gets learning that leads in the classroom activity but is tested with questions that are more real in their life. Therefore, need analysis is needed to collect information about the

students need. It covers the target needs (Goal, necessity, lack, want) and learning needs (Input, procedure, setting, students' role and teacher's role) that will be beneficial to both students and teacher.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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